

New electrochemical sensors used for potentiometric determination of copper and nickel

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The paper presents the experimental and theoretical data regarding the preparation, characterization and analytical applications of four liquid-membrane electrodes. The active substances whose solutions in nitrobenzene have constituted the membranes on graphite rod, are mixed complex combinations of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions with two Schiff base ligands *N*-[2-thienylmethylidene]-2-propanolamine (TNAHP) and *N*-[2-thienylmethylidene]aminopropane (TNAP). The Cu^{II} -selective and Ni^{II} -selective electrodes have been used to determine Cu and Ni ions in aqueous solutions, both by direct potentiometry and potentiometric titration with EDTA. They have also been used for determining Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions in industrial water by direct potentiometry.

In continuation with our attempt to develop ion selective electrodes^{1,2}, we report here the possibility of obtaining Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} selective electrodes with liquid membranes, on the basis of complex combinations of copper with TNAHP³ (for electrode-1) and TNAP³ (for electrode-3) and nickel with TNAHP (for electrode-2) and TNAP (for electrode-4) which have been extracted in nitrobenzene to form ion-selective membranes.

N-[2-thienylmethylidene]-2-propanolamine (TNAHP)

N-[2-thienylmethylidene]aminopropane (TNAP)

Results and Discussion

Response of the electrodes to the concentration of Cu^{II} (Ni^{II}) ions : In Table 1 is presented the electromotive force for the four-ion selective electrodes at 25° and an ionic strength $\mu = 0.4 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3) at different metal ion concentrations.

Influence of pH : It has been found that unlike other types of electrodes, in the case of these liquid ion-selective membrane electrodes, the membranes modify their composition when the aqueous solution is too acidic or too alkaline.

pHs of the samples of aqueous solutions of Cu^{II} (Ni^{II}) were adjusted with buffer solutions⁴. The electrode potentials in acid solutions were found greater than in alkali solutions because in the latter some of the Cu^{II} (Ni^{II}) ions are precipitated as hydroxide.

Table 1. Values of electromotive force (*E*) for the electrodes

Temp. = 25°, ionic strength $\mu = 0.4 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3)

Electrode-1		Electrode-2		Electrode-3		Electrode-4	
[Cu^{II}]	<i>E</i>	[Ni^{II}]	<i>E</i>	[Cu^{II}]	<i>E</i>	[Ni^{II}]	<i>E</i>
<i>M</i>	mV	<i>M</i>	mV	<i>M</i>	mV	<i>M</i>	mV
10^{-1}	350	10^{-1}	335	10^{-1}	403	10^{-1}	390
10^{-2}	320	10^{-2}	305	10^{-2}	373	10^{-2}	361
10^{-3}	291.5	10^{-3}	276	10^{-3}	344	10^{-3}	332
10^{-4}	262	10^{-4}	247.5	10^{-4}	314	10^{-4}	302
10^{-5}	234	10^{-5}	219	10^{-5}	287	10^{-5}	275.5
10^{-6}	205	10^{-6}	190.5	10^{-6}	257	10^{-6}	247

It was deduced experimentally that in the pH ranges 2.3–6.2 for Cu^{II} (electrode-1), 2.0–6.8 for Ni^{II} (electrode-2), 2.2–7.5 for Cu^{II} (electrode-3) and 2.0–7.8 for Ni^{II} (electrode-4), the pH variation does not influence the membrane potential. The experimental results are presented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Influence of pH on the response of the Cu^{II}-selective electrode no 2 with a membrane of [Cu(INAP)₂Cl₂] (curves a and b) respectively of the Cu^{II}-selective electrode no 1 with a membrane of [Cu(TNAHP)₂Cl₂] (curves c and d)

Fig. 2. Influence of pH on the response of the Ni^{II}-selective electrode no 4 with a membrane of [Ni(TNAP)₂Cl₂] (curves a and b) respectively of the Ni^{II}-selective electrode no 2 with a membrane of [Ni(TNAHP)₂Cl₂] (curves c and d)

Selectivity of the electrodes : The electrodes were tested for a series of cations, which participate in equilibrium of ionic exchange with the Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} ions in the membranes. It was found that a series of cations interfere only if they are present in concentrations approximately 1000 times higher as compared to the concentrations of the ions Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}.

For these cations the selectivity constants have been determined by using the reported method⁵. From Table 2 it can be seen that all the electrodes have a cationic response of 29 mV at 25° corresponding to a Nernstian slope of $RT/2F$. The Nernstian response is obeyed in the concentration range 10^{-1} – 10^{-5} M for all the electrodes. As a result, the Cu^{II} (Ni^{II})-selective electrodes can be used for potentiometric determination of copper and nickel.

Table 2. The characteristics of the Cu^{II}- and Ni^{II}-selective electrodes (based on mixed complex combinations)

Temp = 25°, $\mu = 0.4$ M (KNO₃), pH = 4–2

Elec- trode	$\Delta E / \Delta \log c$ mV	Range of linear response (M)	Constants of selectivity to the cations			
			Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Fe ^{II}	Co ^{II}
1	29	10^{-1} – 10^{-5}	–	2.1×10^{-3}	3.52×10^{-4}	5.91×10^{-4}
2	29	10^{-1} – 10^{-5}	1.72×10^{-3}	–	3.68×10^{-4}	5.32×10^{-4}
3	29	10^{-1} – 10^{-5}	–	6.2×10^{-4}	2.18×10^{-4}	3.45×10^{-4}
4	29	10^{-1} – 10^{-5}	1.13×10^{-4}	–	1.60×10^{-4}	2.75×10^{-4}

Dynamic response and the reproducibility of the electrodes The response characteristics of the Cu^{II}- and Ni^{II}-selective electrodes were evaluated by introducing the electrodes in solutions of different concentrations of CuSO₄ and Ni(NO₃)₂, usually ten times higher and by recording the values of the potentials as a function of time.

The response times of the electrodes in diluted solutions (10^{-4} – 10^{-5} M) have been of approximately 2 min, while in more concentrated solutions (10^{-1} – 10^{-3} M) the electrode potential reaches an equilibrium value in a few seconds. The testing of the four electrodes was achieved in 3–5 weeks, noticing that the electrode potentials modify only with ± 2 and ± 3 mV, respectively, without modifying the electrodes slope (29 mV/decade of concentration).

The reproducibility of potential measurements was checked in the concentration range 10^{-1} – 10^{-5} M for the electrodes.

Analytical applications The Cu^{II}- and Ni^{II}-selective electrodes were used for the determination of the copper and nickel ions in aqueous solutions, both by direct potentiometry and by potentiometric titration with EDTA.

For the direct potentiometric determination, a calibration curve was used which was obtained through the variation of the electromotive force of all the ion-selective electrodes as a function of M^{2+} concentrations versus the ESC. The results are presented in Table 1.

The electrodes were tested for the potentiometric titration with EDTA. For the electrodes we obtained potential

rises of 125 mV for electrode-1, 129 mV for electrode-2, 170 mV for electrode-3 and 176 mV for the electrode-4.

Determination of Cu and Ni by direct potentiometry in industrial water : Samples of water from a water cleaning station were analyzed with the electrodes 3 and 4. The concentrations of copper and nickel were also determined for every sample by atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS).

The values obtained of samples of industrial waters taken for analysis through the potentiometric method were in accordance with those obtained through the AAS method. These results are in accordance with the values of the selectivity constants of the electrodes 3 and 4 as compared to Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} , respectively (Table 2). To assert the advantage of using the potentiometric method with the electrodes 3 and 4, all the experimental data were checked through the method of the standard additions.

The study of these four electrodes has proved their primary and secondary characteristics favorable for their practical utilization in potentiometric titrations and in direct potentiometric determinations.

All the prepared electrodes have a wide linear response range to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ ion concentration. For this reason, they are adequate for the potentiometric determination of copper and nickel ions in dilute solutions (dilutions may go down to $10^{-5} M$) as well as in industrial waters.

Experimental

For the preparation of the electroactive membrane, CuSO_4 , $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and nitrobenzene (Merck, G.R.) were used.

Four Cu^{II} - and Ni^{II} -selective electrodes with a liquid membrane were obtained and characterized, out of which the electrodes 1 and 2 had the basis of the mixed complex combinations of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} respectively with *N*-[2-thienylmethylidene]-2-propanolamine, while the electrodes 3 and 4 had the basis of the mixed complex combinations

with *N*-[2-thienylmethylidene]aminopropane of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} , respectively.

The formulation of the complex combinations of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with these two ligands whose solutions in nitrobenzene constituted the membrane on a graphite rod were as follows :

Electrode-1 : $[\text{Cu}(\text{TNAHP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Electrode-3 : $[\text{Cu}(\text{TNAP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Electrode-2 : $[\text{Ni}(\text{TNAHP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Electrode-4 : $[\text{Ni}(\text{TNAP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

The electrodes used for determinations were made according to the reported procedure².

The pH was determined with a Carl-Zeiss-Jena MV 85pH-meter using glass electrode.

The electrochemical system used for measurements was electrochemical cells of the type,

Stainless steel thread	Membrane supported on graphite rod	Analyzed aqueous solution (M^{2+})	KCl saturated	Calomel electrode
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The direct measurement of the potential was made in solutions of CuSO_4 and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ at 25° , ionic strength $\mu = 0.4 M$ (KNO_3) at pH 4 (for electrodes 1 and 3) and 4.2 (for electrodes 2 and 4), using acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer.

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